

Emergence of Artificial Intelligence in Management Concepts & Practices (A study on retailers of Hazaribag)

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence is considered to be the boon for Mankind if used constructively and has got tremendous opportunities in the complex business environment as it is loaded and programmed with immense ability to take rational decisions and perform various Standard and Non standard tasks. In the era of technological advancement where the world is witnessing the digital transformation In order to attain the global automation in various field ,machines are preferred to be the replacement of the the labour and, it is now overtaking the whole management system and is considered as a mechanism to save much of the routine tasks time, However it does have potent threat. This study includes the opportunities and challenges it has brought for the labour market and manager's job roles.

Keywords Artificial Intelligence, Automation, Technological Advancement, Digital Transformation.

Introduction

The term Artificial Intelligence was coined by John McCarthy in 1956 in a conference and its concept was proposed by Allen Turing, in 1950, Allen Newell, J.C Shaw, and Herbert Simon created Logic theorist and first ever running AI software program was formed. Artificial intelligence refers to the ability of the software to perform various task like humans which includes cognition, to reason manipulations similar to actions carried out under the control of the human brain.⁶ It is an information system designed to empower computers with human imitating abilities and skills such as Vision, hearing and learning. Thus, AI is an information computer system built on the basis of human brain and perceptual activity and capable of perceiving the environment, information, learning and responding to external influences, imitating a person.⁵

Providing the machine with the ability to learn is achieved by enable it to learn and rationalize through the use of algorithms so that it can discover the pattern and create insights making the machine capable of making decisions and predictions in the future, so it can be said, it is a machine which learn to perform task that require human reasoning and intelligence.

Objective of study

1. To find out the effectiveness of the AI in Business areas .
2. To understand the status of the AI Implementation in the retailers business activities.
3. To know about the most frequently used AI solution by both customers and business.
4. To know about the challenges faced by the retailers.

Review of Literature

SAR Journal. Volume 4, Issue 1, Pages 34-41, ISSN 2619-9955, DOI: 10.18421/SAR41-06 March 2021. 34, SAR Journal – Volume 4 / Number 1 / 2021. Artificial Intelligence to Improve the Business Efficiency and Effectiveness for Enterprises in Kazakhstan

The research set out to determine the readiness of Kazakhstani businesses for AI, describe cases of AI use in business, identify arising questions, study legal aspects, and present compliance with the existing legal framework.

Al-Zahrani, A., & Marghalani, A. (2018, April 25). How Artificial Intelligent Transform Business. Retrieved from: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3226264> [accessed: 10 December 2020].

The paper discusses different approaches through which AI can transform businesses, including cost reduction, cybersecurity, marketing, innovation, and improved management decision-making.

Methodology

For this study, we decided to choose a descriptive research method. It is a scientific method that involves observing and describing a participant's behaviour. Researcher has used both quantitative and qualitative methods. Also secondary data will be used. The qualitative part of the study includes: Interviews were taken either face-to-face or online using Skype. The quantitative part of the study includes an online survey.

The number of completed interviews is 30. The total number of questions in the questionnaire is 5?

What are the three main challenges related to the development of artificial intelligence in the town?

What are the risks of introducing artificial intelligence technologies in your company?

What are the most popular AI based solution among the customers?

What are the factors associated with the successful implementation of the AI in the business?

What are the impact of AI in the company in the next 5 years?

Based on their extensive experience candidate responded to the interview, the question would determine how effective the AI would be in the respective business area.

Qualitative Research

In the study, we proceeded to take into account the tier II cities to conduct a study, where business is striving for digital transformation. We set a goal to determine the attitude and degree of readiness of business entrepreneur to the implementation and practical application of artificial intelligence, to describe the cases of using artificial intelligence by business here to identify the main questions that arise in business at this stage, to study the application of the AI to various categories ,provide suggestions for eliminating existing barriers and stimulating businesses to implement the technology.

Based on the research conducted , Researcher is planning to conduct interviews with experts in the field of retail. Sample: For the study researcher has taken 30 respondents from retail or small businesses around Hazaribag ,The method of collecting interview is online mode , as it is the most convenient form of data collection.

Methodology and method: For this study, researcher has decided to approach respondent with a descriptive research method, where researcher plan to conduct the interview, and then show the results in charts and graphs.

Types of AI Used in Business

1. Omnichannel customer shopping experience- AI allows retailers to create a seamless customer shopping experience across multiple online, mobile, and in-store channels.

chatbots and virtual assistants, retailers can provide 24/7 customer support, answer customer queries, and offer personalized recommendations.

2. Better -tailored marketing activities- AI helps marketers create better customer segmentation based on insights from audience data.It increase the conversion rate and gain more revenue.

3. Boost customer engagement- AI-powered tools like chatbots and virtual assistants helps in real-time engagement ,which improves customer satisfaction and loyalty. It uses AI to understand customer preferences ,and make personalized promotions.

4. Personalized customer service- AI help retailers offer personalized customer service by analyzing customer data and providing tailored recommendations.

5. Optimized business processes- Implementing AI in retail business provides real-time insights and improves the accuracy and efficiency of decision-making processes.

6. Reduces Human errors and promotecreativity- AI support organizations in reducing labor costs, Automation doesn't mean eliminating redundancies in workplaces and replacing humans with technology.³

Analysis

1. Effectiveness of AI in the business sphere.

Retail companies in Hazaribagare actively introducing AI in their business activities . According to the result of the survey . 60 % of the hazaribag retailers are already planning to installthe AI in their business activity and has been striving for the same. The effectiveness is determined and recorded with certain parameters , 23% of the respondent finds it cost effective as the software installation which incurs one time cost has reduced the recurring expenditure in the long run, 13% respondent agreed to the increase in ROI in their business as AI based tools used for digital marketing would help them gain good insight into customer needs and preferences changing pattern. About 17% of the respondent have expected the improvement in their quality as early detection in the quality failures would help the business to anticipate the problems in advance and take corrective actions in the due time. 20% of the respondent has yet not fixed any criteria to measure its effectiveness. 26% of the respondent have realised it would boost the customer satisfaction due to its personalised recommendation, target offers and customise content.

2 Challenges in implementing AI

Innovation The Research Concept

Implementing AI has been challenging in many aspects and 10 % of the respondent finds it challenging due to its high implementation cost, and in order to work on AI based tools , lot of training is required and hence 23% of the respondent agreed that lack of qualified professional poses a challenge to the company. 30 % of the respondent finds upgrading existing as IT system as a challenge . 20% find customers distrust on AI based tools is potent challenge in the small cities like Hazaribag . 16% of the respondent finds the cyber security as a threat and potent challenge to the small retailers in the region.

3. AI impact on company in next 2 years

According to the respondents prediction the role of AI in the Job creation is least as 20% expect new Job creation in the company after the implementation of the AI. 26% respondent has expected to increase in their productivity, 30% respondent has predicted the innovative development as major impact after AI implementation. 23% of the respondent has predicted the AI based solution would increase their income.

4. Factors influencing successful implementation of AI

There has been various factors which would influence the successful implementation of the AI in the company , 33% of the respondent consider security to the AI based platforms as the most important factor as it would give satisfaction to the employer, employee and customer as their data is secured and private once the trust is inculcated among people, AI would be successfully implemented.

5. Popular AI based solution

According to the retailers the most popular AI based solution which every retailers prefer in the city is personalisation as it gives maximum customer satisfaction due its personalised features such as recommended product, discount offers.

Conclusion

The Interest in the AI is huge in the Hazaribagregion , The leading retail firms are already taking all the steps for developing AI based solutions in their firm , there is no such unified definition of AI . People in small city like Hazaribag are still having stigma with digital transaction and cyber security and face lots of ambiguity with its usage at POS. Retailers the entrepreneurs are yet to learn the application of AI based tools in their business to garner maximum benefit in terms cost reduction , quality control and of monetary benefits.

There should be proper framework for developing AI , which can be attained by the introduction of basic provisions that are universal⁴

Realising its importance at the global level and its wide application , the regulatory barriers for the development of technology should be eliminated .

One should aim to regulate specific system depending upon its area of application so that data mining can be prevented and customers privacy is maintained.

On the basis of the assumption on what could be the future of AI in Hazaribag region the questionnaire was framed . The results were positive and it could be concluded that AI has an effective impact on retail business and very soon entrepreneurs in Hazaribag would establish AI based tools in their business and it will hopefully flourish in next 5 years.

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